

Fire Safety Research Institute (FSRI)-TSA report

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Statement of work

UL's Fire Safety Research Institute would like to investigate the thermal stability of extracted wood components. Contractor (NREL) will perform hemicellulose extraction and flow-through solvolysis to raw biomass to get intact hemicellulose and lignin fractions. These fractions are analyzed by compositional analysis (sugar type and content, lignin content) and chemical analyses; molecular weight distribution by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) and lignin structural analysis by nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.

Contractor will perform the following tasks:

Task 1. Isolation of Hemicellulose from biomass samples.

Task 2. Isolation of native-like lignin through solvolysis.

Task 3. Conduct biomass composition analysis and chemical analyses of isolated hemicellulose and lignin by GPC, DSC and NMR.

Task 4. Sugar linkage analysis of the hemicellulose fraction

Executive Summary

- Pure hemicelluloses were successfully isolated, yielding 0.62 g from 20.8 g of Red Oak and 0.33 g from 18.9 g of Douglas.
- Native-like solvolysis lignin was isolated from both Red Oak (152 mg) and Douglas Fir (230 mg). The chemical structures of both lignins closely resembled those found in the original biomass samples.
- The weight-average molecular weights (M_w) of the isolated lignins were 990 Da for Red Oak and 910 Da for Douglas Fir, with both lignins containing monomeric and dimeric units.
- Both Red Oak and Douglas Fir hemicelluloses retained their acetyl groups, making them water-soluble.
- The Red Oak hemicellulose was predominantly composed of xylan, while the main polysaccharides in Douglas Fir hemicellulose were mannan and xylan.

Results

Task 1. Isolation of Hemicellulose from biomass samples.

There are two primary methods for isolating hemicellulose from biomass: 1) extraction with NaOH, and 2) extraction with DMSO. The NaOH method yields relatively pure hemicellulose but results in the loss of both acetyl groups (which are present in xylan) and other ester groups, such as those found in the lignin-carbohydrate complex.^{1,2} This is because ester bonds are cleaved under basic conditions. In contrast, the DMSO extraction method preserves acetyl and other ester groups since no de-esterification occurs. In this TSA project, FSRI requested the use of the DMSO method for isolating hemicellulose from Red Oak (RO) and Douglas Fir (DF) biomass, as DMSO-extracted hemicellulose more closely resembles its native form.

Scheme 1. Flowchart for the isolation of hemicellulose.

The flowchart for hemicellulose isolation, based on Rowley's method, is shown in **Scheme 1**.³ Non-structural sugars (e.g., sucrose) and non-lignin aromatics (e.g., tannins), which are in whole biomass, can be contaminated into the isolated hemicellulose. To prevent this contamination, extractives were first removed via Soxhlet extraction using water for 48 hours, followed by ethanol (EtOH) extraction for an additional 48 hours. The extractive-free biomass was then delignified using NaClO₄ at 70°C for 3 hours, repeated three times, to remove lignin and remaining aromatic compounds. Delignification conditions were described in **Table 2**.

The resulting delignified biomass (holocellulose, consisting of cellulose and hemicellulose) was subjected to DMSO extraction at 70°C for 3 hours, repeated three times, to yield crude hemicellulose. This was followed by purification with EtOH at room temperature for 12 hours, after which the reaction mixture was filtered and washed with Et₂O to remove residual DMSO and EtOH. The final product was dried in a vacuum desiccator to obtain solid powders. Images of the holocellulose and isolated hemicellulose samples are shown in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Pictures of holocellulose and isolated hemicellulose.

The mass yields of extractives-free biomass, holocellulose, and isolated hemicellulose are summarized in Tables 1–3. The hemicellulose yields from Red Oak (RO) and Douglas Fir (DF) were 3.90 wt% and 2.96 wt%, respectively, based on the holocellulose content. This corresponds to 2.62 wt% and 1.61 wt% yields, respectively, based on the starting whole biomass. These yields are notably lower than those reported for corn stover hemicellulose (7–8 wt% of the starting whole corn stover).³ This difference is likely due to the greater presence of ester and ether bonds between lignin and hemicellulose in RO and DF, which may hinder the extraction process compared to corn stover.

Table 1. Preparation of extractives-free biomass

Entry	Biomass	Whole biomass (g)	Extractives-free biomass (g)	Yield (wt%)	Ave
1	Red Oak 1	6.418	5.4027	84.18	
2	Red Oak 2	6.201	5.3196	85.79	84.98
3	Douglas Fir 1	6.631	5.7069	86.06	
4	Douglas Fir 2	6.517	5.6281	86.36	86.21

Table 2. Delignification of Extractives-free biomass

Entry	Biomass	Extractives-free biomass (g)	NaClO ₄ (g)	37% HCl (ml)	H ₂ O (ml)	Total holocellulose (g)	Yield (wt%)
1	Red Oak	20.84	8.34	1.04	320	16.48	79.06
2	Douglas Fir	18.9	7.56	0.95	320	11.91	63.04

Table 3. Extraction of hemicellulose from holocellulose.

Entry	Biomass	Holocellulose (g)	DMSO (ml)	Isolated Hemicellulose (g)	Yield (wt%)
1	Red Oak	15.84	220 x 3times	0.618	3.90
2	Douglas Fir	11.22	200 x 3times	0.332	2.96

Task 2. Isolation of native-like lignin through Reductive catalytic fractionation (RCF).

Isolation of native lignin from biomass is essential for studying lignin reactions, as it is challenging to understand the chemical reactions and physical changes of each main component (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) in the biomass cell wall when the entire biomass is treated. This difficulty arises from the complex interactions among these components. Isolated lignin provides a clearer understanding of its thermal properties and its behavior during chemical reactions. Several methods for isolating lignin have been reported, with Milled Wood Lignin (MWL) and Cellulolytic Enzyme Lignin (CEL) being considered representative of native lignin.^{4, 5} However, these methods involve time-consuming steps and often yield low amounts of lignin. Recently, a researcher at NREL introduced a flow-through solvolysis method using methanol at 225°C to obtain native-like lignin from poplar.⁶ This method is faster and preserves the integrity of lignin after the solvolysis step. In this TSA project, we adopted the flow-through solvolysis method to isolate lignin from Red Oak (RO) and Douglas Fir (DF) biomass samples.

The schematic for the flow-through solvolysis process is shown in **Figure 2**, following Brandner's method.⁶ Each 5 g biomass sample was placed in a reactor, pressurized to 1600 psig with methanol, and then heated to 200°C with a flow rate of 4 mL/min. The solvolysis liquor was evaporated to remove methanol, followed by liquid-liquid extraction with water and ethyl acetate (EtOAc). The organic layer (EtOAc) was dried over Na₂SO₄ to eliminate any remaining water. EtOAc was then removed using a rotary evaporator to yield the solvolysis lignin, with Red Oak solvolysis lignin and Douglas Fir solvolysis lignin amounts of 152 mg and 230 mg, respectively.

Figure 2. Schematic of flow-through solvolysis of biomass using methanol.

Task 3. Conduct biomass composition analysis and chemical analyses of isolated hemicellulose and lignin by GPC, DSC and NMR.

The compositional analysis data for the original biomass, solvolysis pulp (solid residue), and hemicellulose are summarized in **Table 4**. Since the isolated lignin samples were limited in quantity, the estimated compositional data for the lignin samples were calculated by subtracting the component concentrations in the solvolysis pulp from those in the original biomass, using the pulp yields of 68.72 wt% for Red Oak (RO) and 72.38 wt% for Douglas Fir (DF) as conversion factors. The original Red Oak (RO) biomass contains 26.3% lignin, 38.6% glucan, and 19.0% xylan, while the original Douglas Fir (DF) biomass contains 32.5% lignin, 41.2% glucan, and 9.2% mannan.

The isolated RO hemicellulose consists of 16.0% lignin and 62.6% xylan, while DF hemicellulose contains 35.9% lignin, 16.2% xylan, and 23.8% mannan. According to the compositional analysis, both hemicelluloses contain measurable amounts of lignin. However, both FTIR and NMR data suggest that the lignin content in the hemicelluloses is minimal. This discrepancy is primarily due to the low sample amounts available for compositional analysis. The NREL standard protocol for biomass analysis requires 300 mg of sample for a comprehensive compositional analysis,⁷ but only 50 mg of each hemicellulose was available, as approximately 100 mg of hemicellulose was obtained in the initial extraction. Additionally, carbohydrates may undergo hydrolysis, forming furfural and its condensation products, which are often referred to as “pseudo-lignin.” These products share similar properties with actual lignin and can contribute to an overestimation of lignin content in the analysis.

Table 4. Compositional analysis data of virgin biomass, isolated lignin and hemicellulose from Red Oak and Douglas Fir.

Sample Description	%Total Ash	%Total Protein	%Water Extractives	%Ethanol Extractives	(% Acid Soluble Lignin)	% Lignin	% Glucan	% Xylan	% Galactan	% Arabinan	%Mannan	%Acetyl	Total %
Red Oak Virgin	0.20	1.49	3.99	3.96	6.24	26.32	38.62	18.95	1.63	0.00	1.00	3.18	99.36
Douglas Fir Virgin	0.17	0.86	4.30	4.67	4.23	32.53	41.22	2.90	2.70	0.00	9.18	0.55	99.07
Red Oak Pulp (Ave)	0.3	1.05	–	–	5.78	16.10	55.33	24.29	1.03	0.00	1.51	1.81	101.40
Douglas Fir Pulp (Ave)	4.33	1.03	–	–	3.57	29.32	47.30	3.02	4.25	0.00	11.21	0.51	100.96
Isolated lignin (DF)	–	3.20			9.47	63.55	2.52	9.43	3.87	0.00	0.00	8.09	100.12
Isolated lignin (RO)	–	0.55			7.59	52.27	32.26	3.30	0.00	0.00	4.92	0.85	101.76
Red Oak Hemicellulose	–	–	–	–	11.99	15.98	2.29	62.61	1.45	0.09	0.98	7.62	91.02
Douglas Fir Hemicellulose	–	–	–	–	24.94	35.87	12.83	16.23	5.33	0.44	23.76	1.62	96.08

The molecular weight distribution of the isolated lignin and hemicellulose samples was analyzed using gel permeation chromatography (GPC) (**Figure 3**).⁸ The weight-average molecular weight (*M_w*) of the Red Oak (RO) and Douglas Fir (DF) lignins were found to be 990 Da and 910 Da, respectively, with similar polydispersity (PD) values for both lignins. Notably, DF lignin has a slightly lower *M_w* compared to RO lignin.

In contrast, the molecular weight distribution of the hemicelluloses revealed distinct differences. The RO hemicellulose exhibited a low *M_w* of 290 Da, corresponding to disaccharides, while the DF hemicellulose displayed a significant portion in the 200–300 Da range, and a broader range of peaks of oligosaccharide extending from 3K to 100K Da. This difference is likely due to incomplete derivatization (acetylation) of the hemicellulose samples, which resulted in the polysaccharide portion with higher molecular weights not being detected under the current GPC conditions.

Figure 3. GPC chromatograms of (A) isolated lignin and (B) hemicellulose from Red Oak and Douglas Fir.

The FTIR spectra of the isolated hemicellulose samples are shown in **Figure 4**, with each peak assigned according to previous references.^{9, 10} Both hemicellulose samples exhibit strong OH stretching and C-H stretching absorptions in the ranges of 3100-3600 cm^{-1} and 2850-3000 cm^{-1} , respectively. A distinct peak at 1750 cm^{-1} corresponds to the acetyl carbonyl group, clearly indicating the presence of acetyl groups in both hemicelluloses. A small absorption between 1620-1650 cm^{-1} represents the asymmetric stretching vibration of the carboxyl group from glucuronic acid in the hemicellulose.

The peak at 1500 cm^{-1} , associated with aromatic ring stretching and vibration in lignin, is observed in the DF hemicelluloses, though it is tiny in the RO hemicellulose. Additionally, a small band around 1235 cm^{-1} is observed in the DF hemicellulose, corresponding to the C-O stretching of the guaiacyl unit in lignin, while this band is absent in the RO hemicellulose. These findings suggest that the RO hemicellulose contains a negligible amount of lignin, while the DF hemicellulose contains a small amount of lignin. This observation contradicts the results from the compositional analysis (**Table 4**). The broad bands in the 950-1150 cm^{-1} range are attributed to C-O-C, C-OH, and C-O stretching vibrations in cellulose and hemicellulose. Overall, the FTIR spectra align with the expected structural characteristics of typical hemicellulose.

Figure 4. FTIR chromatograms of hemicellulose from Red Oak and Douglas Fir.

The isolated hemicellulose samples were further analyzed using ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR spectroscopy (**Figure 5**). On the ^1H -NMR spectra of both hemicelluloses, a clear peak for the acetyl (OAc) group appeared at 2.1 ppm, indicating the presence of acetyl groups on the xylan backbone. Additionally, typical methine (-CH-) peaks from the glycosyl units were observed in the 3.0–4.5 ppm range. The anomeric protons, H1 α and H1 β , appeared at 5.4 ppm and 5.2 ppm, respectively. Tiny aromatic peaks were detected between 5.5 and 7.5 ppm, suggesting a negligible contamination of lignin in both isolated hemicelluloses.

On the ^{13}C -NMR spectra (**Figure 5B**), the anomeric carbon (C1) was observed between 100 and 105 ppm, while the C2, C3, and C4 peaks were in the 70–80 ppm range, and the C5 peak appeared at 63.4 ppm. These patterns indicate that the Red Oak hemicellulose closely matches the expected xylan structure, which is consistent with the compositional analysis showing xylan as the predominant component in RO hemicellulose. For Douglas Fir, the ^{13}C -NMR spectrum showed several peaks in the C1 and C2–4 regions, with a prominent peak at 60.5–61 ppm, corresponding to C6 of glucan (Glc-6) and mannan (Man-6). Additional peaks were observed at 80–85 ppm, corresponding to C4 of glucan (Glc-4) and mannan (Man-4). This is consistent with the compositional analysis, which indicated that mannan is the dominant sugar in DF hemicellulose (23.8%), followed by xylan (16.2%) (**Table 4**). The ^1H and ^{13}C -NMR data indicate that both hemicelluloses retain acetyl groups and are relatively pure, confirming their native-like structure.

Figure 5. ¹H and ¹³C-NMR spectra of isolated hemicellulose from Red Oak and Douglas Fir.

The thermal properties of the isolated lignin samples were analyzed using Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) and Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). The TGA thermogram and DSC curves are shown in **Figure 6**. Both lignins exhibited a 3% mass loss around 100°C, while the steam-explosion lignin degraded at temperatures above 200°C.¹¹ Notably, the DF lignin exhibited a gel-like consistency, likely due to the presence of 4-propylguaiacol, a high-viscosity monomeric product of lignin solvolysis, which is found in some amounts in DF lignin.

To measure the glass transition temperature (*T_g*) of both lignin samples, they were solidified at -90°C using liquid nitrogen and then gradually heated. Both lignins softened around 23°C and continued to soften as the temperature increased. However, due to early degradation, the *T_g* of both lignins could not be accurately determined. For comparison, the *T_g* of steam-explosion lignin was previously reported to be 159°C.¹¹ These TGA and DSC data suggest that both solvolysis Red Oak (RO) and Douglas Fir (DF) lignins contain a certain proportion of monomeric and dimeric units, which contribute to their lower stiffness compared to typical steam-explosion lignin. This conclusion is further supported by the GPC data, which indicate that both lignins contain low-molecular-weight compounds (100-300 Da) in the range of 10-15% (**Figure 3A**).

Figure 6. TGA and DSC of Red Oak and Douglas Fir lignin samples.

To understand the structure and linkage type in isolated lignin, they were also analyzed two-dimensional nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) of HSQC (Heteronuclear Single Quantum Coherence) NMR. HSQC spectra were shown in **Figure 7**. Lignin consists of different units shown in **Figure 7**. The aryl glycerol- β -aryl ether (β -O-4) unit is generally predominant in most of hardwood and softwood lignin, and softwood lignin mainly consist of guaiacyl (G) type unit, and a hardwood lignin is from a mixture of guaiacyl (G) and syringyl (S) units. Whole cell wall components in the original Red Oak contain S, oxidized S (S') and G peaks as well as β -O-4, phenylcoumaran (β -5) and pinoresinol (β - β) interunit linkages with polysaccharide (**Figure 7A**).^{12, 13} The Red Oak solvolysis lignin has similar peaks in aromatic region (δ_H/δ_C 6.0-8.0/100-150 ppm) with much less polysaccharide peaks (black color), suggesting that the RO solvolysis lignin preserve original Red Oak lignin structure (**Figure 7B**). The original Douglas Fir consists of mainly G units with a little amount of p-hydroxyphenyl (P) unit, and β -O-4, β -5 and β - β interunits as well (**Figure 7C**). Compared with original Red Oak, the original DF has more aldehydes at δ_H/δ_C 9.5-10/190-200 ppm. The Douglas Fir solvolysis lignin has similar peaks with much less polysaccharide but more aliphatic peaks (-CH₃-, -CH₂-, -CH-) at δ_H/δ_C 0.5-2.5/0-50 ppm (**Figure 7D**). This indicates that purity of the DF lignin is high but contains hydrocarbons due to lignin and sugar degradation during solvolysis step. Overall, both lignin sample persist original lignin structure with a little amount sugar.

Figure 7. HSQC NMR spectra of Red Oak and Douglas Fir lignin samples.

Task 4. Sugar linkage analysis of the hemicellulose fraction

Hemicellulose is composed of various polysaccharides, including xylan, galactan, arabinan, and mannan, which are primarily connected by ether bonds. To analyze the linkage types, traditional linkage analysis methods, combining permethylation and the alditol acetate method, were applied to the hemicellulose samples. This approach involves five steps: 1) reduction of carboxylic acids using NaBD₄, 2) methylation of all hydroxyl groups, 3) acid hydrolysis to cleave ether bonds, 4) acetylation of the hydroxy groups to generate alditol acetates, and 5) GC-MS analysis. However, after several trials, it was found that permethylation and/or subsequent acid hydrolysis with TFA did not proceed completely, yielding insufficient amounts of alditol acetates. Given the limited amount of hemicellulose, HSQC NMR was used as an alternative analytical technique.

The HSQC spectra of both hemicellulose samples are shown in **Figure 8**. The peaks were assigned based on reference data.^{14, 15} The Red Oak (RO) hemicellulose primarily displayed cross-peaks corresponding to (1→4)-β-D-xylopyranose units, along with smaller signals for 4-O-methyl-α-D-glucuronic acid at 5.2/97, 4.35/70, and 3.2/80.5 ppm. Additionally, peaks at 4.6/99.1, 4.2/61.8, and 3.3/74.7 ppm were assigned to (1→4)-β-D-Xylp-2-O-(4-O-methyl-α-D-glucuronic acid). Compositional analysis revealed that RO hemicellulose is predominantly composed of 63% xylan and 2.3% glucan, suggesting a potential structure of (1→4)-β-D-xylopyranose-2-O-(4-O-methyl-α-D-glucuronic acid)-D-xylan in the RO hemicellulose.

The same cross-peaks for (1→4)-β-D-Xylp and 4-O-methyl-α-D-glucuronic acid were also observed in the Douglas Fir (DF) hemicellulose. However, the peak area for (1→4)-β-D-Xylp-2-O-(4-O-methyl-α-D-glucuronic acid) was larger in DF than in RO. In addition, prominent peaks for α-D-mannopyranoside were observed, along with small peaks for (1→4)-β-D-glucopyranoside. Interestingly, a small peak for α-L-arabinofuranoside was detected, even though arabinan content

was only 0.44% by compositional analysis. Galactan (5.3%) was also present in DF hemicellulose. Based on the HSQC NMR and compositional analysis data, the main structures of DF hemicellulose are proposed to include: 1) a mannan backbone with a xylan chain: (1→6)-β-D-Manp-(1→6)-β-D-Manp-(1→4)-β-D-Xylp; 2) a mannan backbone with galactan and xylan: (1→6)-β-D-Manp-(1→5)-β-D-Galf-(1→4)-β-D-Xylp; 3) a xylan backbone with glucan: (1→4)-β-D-Xylp-(1→4)-β-D-Glcp; and 4) a xylan backbone with glucuronic acid: (1→4)-β-D-xylopyrano-2-O-(4-O-methyl-α-D-glucuronic acid)-D-xylan.

Additionally, a methoxyl peak at 3.8/55.6 ppm was observed, suggesting that both hemicellulose samples contain small amounts of lignin, which is consistent with the compositional analysis data.

Figure 8. HSQC NMR spectra of Red Oak and Douglas Fir hemicellulose samples.

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